

Ferrocene Derivatives. Part-I. Synthesis of some Ferrocenyl-pyrimidobenzimidazole, -triazolopyrimidine, -pyrazolopyridine and -pyrimidine as Antimicrobial Agents†

MOHAMED ABBAS METWALLY*, EZZ E. M. KANDEL and FATHY A. AMER

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Mansoura University, Mansoura, Egypt

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Condensation of 1-acetylferrocene with different aromatic aldehydes resulted in the formation of the α , β -unsaturated ketones (2a-c). The reactivity of 2 towards 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole, 2-aminobenzimidazole, 1-phenyl-3-aminopyrazolone and guanidine hydrochloride to give the linear structures 3, 5, 7 and 8 have been investigated. The structures of the hitherto unknown ring systems have been confirmed by pmr, ir and mass spectral data.

The antibacterial activity of various nitrogen heterocycles is well known¹, while the application of ferrocene system to medicinal chemistry has not been investigated in a large scale^{2,3}. We report herein the synthesis of compounds containing both of these groups.

Acetylferrocene (1) is typical acylferrocene, and undergoes the usual transformation of aryl ketones. Thus, the ferrocenyl chalcones (2a-c) were prepared by the interaction of 1 with benzaldehyde, *p*-anisaldehyde and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde in the presence of alcoholic 4% potassium hydroxide. Derivatives 2a, c were reported previously^{4,5}.

a, Ar = C₆H₅
b; Ar = C₆H₄.OOCH₃-*p*
c; Ar = C₆H₄.OH-*p*

The reactivity of 2 towards 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole, 2-aminobenzimidazole, 1-phenyl-3-amino-2-pyrazolin-5-one and guanidine to give the linear structures 3, 5, 7 and 8 have been investigated. The reaction of 2b with 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole in absolute ethanol afforded 7-ferrocenyl-5,6-dihydro-5-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-*s*-triazolo[4,3-*a*]pyrimidine (3), rather than the possible structure (4). The formation of 3 finds support from the absence of the carbonyl and NH absorptions in its ir spectrum. The assignment of the linear structure (3) is consistent with the observations made in our previous publication^{6,7}.

Compound 3 gave molecular ion [M]⁺ at *m/z* 412 corresponding to C₂₂H₂₀N₄FeO. It is of interest to note that contrary to the general pattern with metallocenes the molecular ion is not the base peak in this compound⁸.

The condensation of 2b with 2-aminobenzimidazole in absolute ethanol (molar ratio) gives a product (70%), m.p. > 300°. The ir spectra of this product does not show any carbonyl absorption. It thus appears that the product has either structure 5 or 6, both consistent with molecular formula C₂₇H₂₅N₅FeO, obtained by elemental analysis. However, the ir spectra favours structure 5 (no absorptions due to NH). The formation of 5 finds support from our previous work on the condensation of 2-arylidene-1,3-indandions with 2-aminobenzimidazole⁷ to give the linear products. Compound 5 gave no molecular ion, but the observed fragment *m/z* 345, corresponding to C₂₀H₁₉NFeO, was obviously formed by loss of C₇H₄N₂ from the parent ion. The fragment *m/z* 345 had been observed also in the spectra of some ferrocene derivatives¹⁰.

The fragments *m/z* 121, 56 and 65 were characteristics for the spectra of ferrocene⁹. Thus the structure of 5 was settled to be 2-ferrocenyl-3,4-dihydro-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)pyrimido[1,2-*a*]benzimidazole.

†Part-3 in the series of heterocyclic compounds with bridge-head nitrogen. For part 2, see M. A. Metwally and H. A. Etman, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1986, 41, 486.

In connection with the above condensations 3-amino-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one was reacted with **2b** to afford 6-ferrocenyl-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-2-phenyl-3*H*-pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridin-3-one (**7**). The ir spectra of **7** showed absorption at 1670 cm^{-1} (CO pyrazolone). In the mass spectrum, no molecular ion was observed, but the fragment m/z 370 corresponding to $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{NFeO}$, was obviously formed by the loss of $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}$ from the parent ion (see Experimental).

Gaundine hydrochloride was condensed with **2b** to afford 2-amino-6-ferrocenyl-4,5-dihydro-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)pyrimidine (**8**). It is of interest to note that, the molecular ion is the base peak in **8** (see Experimental).

In the ^1H nmr spectra, the deshielding effect of the $\text{C}=\text{N}$ causes the protons of the substituted-cyclopentadienyl ring to be shifted downfield, the $\text{H}_{2,5}$ protons occurring at δ 5.8–5.7, and the $\text{H}_{3,4}$ protons at δ 4.7–4.6 relative to the unshifted C_5H_5 protons at δ 4.5–4.4. The chalcone (**2b**) exhibits shielding with the $\text{H}_{2,5}$ protons at δ 4.9 and the $\text{H}_{3,4}$ protons at δ 4.8. The two proton absorption for the methylene group is found at δ 3.6–3.9. The absence of vinyl group in **2b** is noted. In addition to the ferrocene and the aromatic protons, ^1H nmr spectra had a peak at δ 4.2–4.4 (CH). The appearance of a peak at δ 3.7–3.9 (OCH_3) was noticed, in addition to the aromatic signals at δ 7.6–9.1.

Experimental

Melting points (uncorrected) were determined on a Gallenkamp electric melting point apparatus. Microanalyses of the elements (C, H) were determined at Microanalytical Laboratory, Faculty of Science, Mansoura University. Ir spectra were recorded in KBr. ^1H nmr spectra were determined

on a Varian 90 apparatus in CDCl_3 . Mass spectra were measured on a Varian Mat 711, direct inlet at 70 eV.

Ferrocenyl chalcones (2a–c): Derivatives **2a, c** were reported previously (m. p. and m. m. p.)^{4,5}. Compound **2b** formed reddish-brown crystals, (90%), m. p. 123° (Found: C, 69.53; H, 5.12. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{FeO}_2$ requires: C, 69.38; H, 5.24%).

7-Ferrocenyl-5,6-dihydro-5-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-s-triazolo[4,3-*a*]pyrimidine (3): A solution of **2b** (0.001 mol) and 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole (0.001 mol) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 20 h. The reaction mixture was left to stand for 24 h, the solid product obtained was then filtered off and recrystallised from ethanol to give **3** as deep brown crystals (65%), m.p. $> 300^\circ$ d (Found: C, 64.48; H, 5.12. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_3\text{FeO}$ requires: C, 64.09; H, 4.89%; ν_{max} 1590 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{N}$); m/z (rel. int.) 412.25 [M^+] (1) (Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_3\text{FeO}$: 412.25), 347 ($M - \text{C}_5\text{H}_5$) (24), 346 (347–H) (100), 344 (346–2H) (7), 316 (344– N_2) (1), 185 ($M^+ - \text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_4\text{O}$) (7) and 120 (347– $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_4\text{O}$) (70).

2-Ferrocenyl-3,4-dihydro-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)pyrimido[1,2-*a*]benzimidazole (5): A mixture of **2b** (0.001 mol) and 2-aminobenzimidazole (0.001 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) was boiled under reflux for 24 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated under vacuum. The precipitated solid obtained after cooling was recrystallised from ethanol to give **5** as a reddish-brown crystals (75%), m.p. $> 300^\circ$ d (Found: C, 69.91; H, 4.91; N, 8.79. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{FeO}$ requires: C, 70.29; H, 5.02; N, 9.1%; ν_{max} 1600 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{N}$); m/z (rel. int.) 345 ($M - \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}_2$) (1,2), 238 (345– $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3$) (1), 173 (238– C_5H_5) (1,2), 133 (173– CH_2CN) (100), 121 (133–C) (7), 56 (121– C_5H_5) (15) and 65 (121–Fe) (33).

6-Ferrocenyl-2,3a-4,5-tetrahydro-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-2-phenyl-3*H*-pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridin-3-one (7): A solution of **2b** (0.0001 mol) and 3-amino-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (0.0001 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 18 h. The reaction mixture was set aside at room temperature till a solid product obtained, which was filtered off and recrystallised from ethanol to give compound **7** as deep brown red crystals (70%), m.p. $> 300^\circ$ (Found: C, 68.74; H, 4.75; N, 8.56. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_3\text{FeO}_2$ requires: C, 69.19; H, 5.0; N, 8.34%; ν_{max} 1600 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) and 1685 (cm^{-1}) ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ of pyrazolone); m/z (rel. int.) 370 ($M - \text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}$) (1), 346 (370– C_2) (6), 345 (370– C_2H) (2), 238 (345– $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3$) (1), 173 (238– C_5H_5) (2), 133 (173– CH_2CN) (14), 121 (133–C) (18) and 93 (100).

2-Amino-6-ferrocenyl-4,5-dihydro-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-pyrimidine (8): A mixture of **2b** (0.01 mol), guandidine hydrochloride (0.01 mol) and sodium acetate (0.5 g) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 20 h. The reaction mixture after cooling, was poured into ice-water. The solid product that obtained, was filtered off and recrystallised from ethanol to give compound **8** as brown

crystals (50%), m.p. $> 300^\circ$ (Found: C, 62.43; H, 5.51; N, 9.97. $C_{21}H_{23}N_3FeO_2$ requires: C, 62.22; H, 5.71; N, 10.36%); ν_{max} 1605 cm^{-1} (C=N); m/z (rel. int.) 405.29 [M]⁺ (100) (calcd. for $C_{21}H_{23}N_3FeO_2$, 405.29), 387 (405 - H_2O) (3), 254 (387 - $p-OCH_3C_6H_4-C\equiv N$) (10), 185 (254 - $C_8H_5N_2$) (9), 121 (185 - C_8H_5) (67), 65 (121 - Fe) (49) and 56 (121 - C_8H_8) (59).

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